

TEACHERS' LIVED EXPERIENCES IN TEACHING SCIENCE DURING THE PANDEMIC

Michelle F. Bayot, MAEd- General Science

*Bayawan City Science and Technology Education Center- Elementary,
Banga Bayawan City 6221, Negros Oriental, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative study explored the lived experiences of elementary school teachers in teaching Science during the COVID-19 pandemic. The participants of this research were the teachers from Bayawan City schools adopting modular learning modality, whose ages range from 39 to 59 years old, and whose length of teaching experience ranges from 16 to 36 years. Data were collected by means of recorded interviews and were analyzed using Colaizzi's Method. Key findings revealed four (4) emergent themes representing the science teachers' lived experiences. The themes cover the various teaching constraints and challenges, teacher interventions, and sense of accomplishment experienced by the teachers during the pandemic. Data revealed that the participants faced major changes in terms of science teaching instruction and strategies to adapt to the shift to modular learning modality and the hindrances to interaction, communication, and experimentation due to home learning setup. The teachers also experienced changes in terms of extended work hours, additional work functions, concerns on student output completion and submission, and compromise in academic integrity. Parental involvement was identified as a significant factor in the teaching-learning process during the pandemic. Teachers also expressed relatively good perceptions of teaching effectiveness and satisfaction. Recommendations were provided to improve the current teaching conditions of teachers and learning conditions of students under the modular learning modality.

Keywords: lived experience, science teachers, modular learning modality, Philippines, COVID-19 pandemic

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 outbreak has been adversely affecting all segments of the population, particularly those individuals in the most vulnerable social groups such as those living in poverty, the elderly, people with disabilities, the youth, and the indigenous peoples (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2020). Certainly, it has also affected the educational sector. Education around the world has changed tremendously as a result of the global pandemic (Li & Lalani, 2020). Many countries have closed schools, colleges, and universities in 2020 to reduce the risk of spreading the viral infection, thereby altering people's attitudes, relationships, and lifestyles (Simbulan, 2020).

In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) has issued DepEd Order No. 012, Series of 2020, establishing the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP), a bundle of education interventions designed to address the educational problems posed by COVID-19. The BELCP was developed to safeguard the health and safety of pupils, teachers, and workers and to provide learning continuity during the pandemic through curricular changes, the structuring of learning materials, and the use of numerous sources of information. This change in the modality of lesson delivery resulted in many struggles in terms of implementation.

A study by Dangle and Sumaoang (2020) identified that secondary level teachers have encountered challenges such as the lack of school funds for module design and distribution, pupils' struggles with self-study, and parents' inability to intellectually manage their child/children. Nonetheless, teachers have looked for strategies to undertake remote modes of teaching since mobility in delivering instruction to pupils has been limited. Also, secondary level teachers in the Philippines, especially in teaching Science using the distance learning modality, have familiarized themselves with the different learning platforms to develop professional skills necessary for the effective implementation of the learning modality. Moreover, they have upgraded their equipment, identified teaching methodologies that can be applied in learning, and conducted tests by incorporating more practical questions (Arrieta et al., 2020).

The researcher of the current study believes in the necessity to look deeper into what teachers have gone through during these times of the pandemic especially that there are only limited studies that explored on unique teacher experiences amidst Covid-19, particularly the experiences of elementary science teachers in public schools. Hence, the purpose of this study is to investigate, acknowledge, and identify the various lived experiences of the indicated group of educators in the context of modular learning modality.

Furthermore, this undertaking is deemed as a means to gather baseline data on the challenges faced by teachers while promoting continuity of education during these

trying times, which will also aid in the development of more effective teaching methodologies and academic strategies for future use.

Research Questions

The research study aims to explore the lived experiences of the teachers as to their teaching of the Science subject during the pandemic. The grand question that this study intends to answer is:

“What are the lived experiences of teachers in terms of teaching Science during the pandemic?”

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a phenomenological research design, a qualitative research method that is used to describe how humans experience a certain phenomenon (Creswell, 2013). Phenomenology, as a qualitative method, asks a different question to further explicate the meaning of the phenomenon (Guillbeau, 2014). The phenomenological design allowed the researcher to use texts to make sense of the phenomenon which, in the case of the study, are the lived experiences of science teachers in delivering instruction during the pandemic.

This research design attempts to search for the essential meaning of the teachers' experiences and identify some congruent themes and underlying structure to the experiences (Maxwell, 2012). As determined in an investigation on qualitative studies, particularly phenomenological research, the participants are chosen through criterion purposive sampling. Criterion purposive sampling is a non-random technique that utilizes identified participants that meet a defined, predetermined criterion (Palinkas et al., 2015; Moser & Korstjens, 2017). In phenomenology, the researcher shall select individuals that can purposefully form an understanding of the research problem and the central phenomenon under study (Creswell, 2013).

For this inquiry, these criteria are considered in selecting the research participants: (a) elementary school teachers handling Science subjects; (b) must be active in service during the learning continuity effective amidst the COVID-19 pandemic; (c) aged 39 years old and above; and (d) whose length of teaching experience is over 15 years. Through these qualifications, 8 Science teachers from public elementary schools under the Division of Bayawan City were identified. To confirm data saturation, 2 participants were interviewed but their responses were not included in the presentation.

This study was conducted in the respective homes of the participants or in the mutually agreed place by both the participants and the researcher. The participants have

been teaching in the public elementary schools of the Division of Bayawan City, namely, Bayawan City East Central School and Banga Elementary School. Methodically evaluating qualitative data would result in the development of emergent themes and patterns. Data analysis typically entails breaking down data into smaller units, coding and naming the units based on the content they represent, and grouping coded materials based on Fourth, formulated meanings were shared concepts (Polit & Beck, 2013).

In this study, Colaizzi's Phenomenological Method, which is deemed appropriate for content analysis, was employed. Beck and Watson (2008) maintained that Colaizzi's method achieves objectivity in data analysis and takes into account its fidelity to phenomena and that it entails a respectful listening to what the phenomenon speaks of itself, rather than telling what it is. The steps involved in this method are as follows:

First, the researcher recorded all interviews and transcribed the information verbatim. Listening to the recorded files is important because it creates a sense of connection, and reading the transcripts repeatedly allows the researcher to develop a sense of meaning for each transcript. Therefore, the researcher must be trained in taking notes to aid in reflexive practice while listening, reading, and rereading (Tessier, 2012; Sanders, 2003).

Second, significant statements or phrases relating directly to the research phenomenon were extracted from the transcripts of the participants. To identify important statements in the transcripts that truly tell the lived experiences of the study participants, careful analysis of the statements in the transcript is required. It has been established that manual transcription and analysis would allow for continued immersion in the data, and whatever thoughts and feelings arise during this stage would be recorded in the reflexive diary and be later used to describe some interpretative decisions (Praveena, 2021; Sanders, 2003).

Third, formulated meanings were constructed from the significant statements. Cornelia (2012) stated that the formulated meanings should accurately reflect the intent of each statement. This necessitates a comparison of the original transcript, significant statements, and formulated meanings generated by all participants. The third stage now demands conscientious reflexivity that acknowledges any presuppositions in order to avoid misinterpretation of the participants' perspectives.

Fourth, formulated meanings were organized into theme clusters, which will evolve into emergent themes. To accurately reflect the meaning of the experiences, these themes are constantly checked and refined against the original transcripts. This requires multiple rounds of cross-referencing.

Fifth, the results were incorporated into a rich and exhaustive description of the lived experiences of Science teachers while teaching during the COVID 19 pandemic. According to Denzin and Lincoln (2017), detail, context, emotion, and the webs of social relationships that connect persons to one another, as well as the voices, feelings, actions, and meanings of interacting individuals, should all be included in an exhaustive

description that goes beyond facts and appearances. Furthermore, it is suggested that this is rechecked by the research adviser for feedback and accuracy.

Sixth, which is the most important stage, involves getting validation from the people who took part in the study as regards the exhaustive description of their experiences. This requires returning to the participants for confirmation and possible follow-up interview to ensure that the recorded statements accurately reflected their experiences. Their remarks will be meticulously documented.

Lastly, the researcher incorporated any new or pertinent data obtained from the participants' validation and used it to achieve congruence with the participants' lived experience.

The seven steps, along with a continuous review and verification procedure, were meticulously followed by the researcher to ensure that the findings accurately reflect the Science teachers' experiences during the pandemic.

RESULTS

To assure the credibility, consistency, and trustworthiness of the data collection and analysis, the rigor of the study was done through: (a) active listening during the conduct of the interview, (b) careful coding to obtain rich and comprehensive data; (c) audio recording interviews for transcription; (d) audit trail; (e) doing reflexive journaling; and (f) conclusion with experts or advisers.

It is good to note that the proponent is a science teacher belonging to the same schools' division, which is Bayawan City Division, as with the participants. Some of the participants are known to the researcher. However, to mitigate the influence of personal biases and preconceived notions, the researcher made sure to keep cognizant of this possible occurrence.

The main role of the researcher during the interview was to facilitate the flow of thoughts and ideas, and to collect substantive information on the different narratives expressed by the participants with the use of prompts and points of clarification. Aside from having an audio recording of the interview, non-verbal cues were logged through journaling.

Coding was done during the analysis and interviews. This ensured that the information that was collected during the individual interviews was kept confidential. The participants were aware that their involvement and their inputs were to be treated with utmost confidentiality and that their identities were to be kept unidentified all throughout course of the study.

The participants were also asked to sign the informed consent forms before the conduct of interviews. Open-ended questions were primarily used during the interview

proper. All questions were asked in English, but the participants were given the liberty to speak in the vernacular so that they could freely express their ideas and thoughts.

After a thorough analysis of the transcripts and coding, the researcher identified the following 4 emergent themes with twelve clustered themes capturing the lived experiences of the Science teachers during the pandemic:

Figure 2. Emergent and Clustered Themes on the Lived Experience

This study explored the lived experiences of science teachers while teaching during the pandemic. It sought to answer the questions: (1) What are the lived experiences of the teachers in teaching Science during the pandemic? (2) How do the teachers describe their experiences during the pandemic?

Eight participants were interviewed using open-ended questions. After a thorough analysis of the transcripts, four emergent themes emerged along with twelve clustered themes. The twelve clustered themes are as follows:

Pupil Preparedness and Instructional Limitations. The ability of science teachers to teach science during the pandemic is affected by the physical distance resulting in the difficulty in establishing constant communication and the absence of interaction between pupils and teacher. This further led to instructional limitations as instructions are usually written and the chance to distribution of the self-learning modules, explain it more thoroughly is limited. The unpreparedness of the pupils for modular learning as well as their lack of reading comprehension affects the accomplishment of modules.

Teaching Techniques Limitations. Many of the participants made mention of their inability to utilize teaching strategies in the modular learning modality that were deemed to be effective during the face-to-face setup. Experimentation, one of the main strategies to achieve learning competencies in science teaching, has been modified due to the inaccessibility of the school laboratories and lab equipment/materials. The teachers have adopted measures that allowed pupils to perform experiments requiring materials that were readily accessible to them at home.

Pupil's Learning Conditions. The demand for supplementary equipment like gadgets has become more prevalent in the modular learning modality. Cellphones have become a necessity as these allow instant communication with teachers and access to vital information and supplementary learning resources like videos. The participants have revealed the learning limitations and restrictions of pupils during the pandemic given the fact that there are pupils who have no access to the internet and technology.

Parental Involvement. One of the major players in the context of pandemic learning is the parents. The extent of learning of the pupil is contingent to the parent's proactiveness and willingness to guide and carry out necessary interventions at home to help ease the understanding of the learners especially in understanding abstract concepts or ideas. The participants mentioned that the educational attainment of the parents has an influence on the quality of the outputs of the pupils.

Planning and Preparation. The participants shared how the pandemic has contributed to the extension of their functions to facilitate learning. These functions include reproduction, sorting, and preparation for worksheets, and answer sheets. This scenario gave rise to issues on time management and overall performance of teachers.

Completion of Learning Outputs. Among the major concerns disclosed by the participants in terms of pupils' performance during the pandemic is the learners' failure to comply with all the outputs and completely answer the worksheets given to them. This goes back to the parents' extent of participation in motivating their children to comply with the requirements and accomplish all work loads.

Compromised Academic Integrity. Some participants have exposed certain profound breaches of academic integrity in terms of the completion and fulfillment of modules. The participants have observed that the accomplishment of the modules is no longer done by the pupils but by their parents or guardians. It could be noted that teachers have exhibited tolerance to this practice of dishonesty and tend to be considerate due to the inopportune circumstances brought by the pandemic.

Parent-Teacher Dialogue. Majority of the participants talked about the implications of having a good established line of communication between parents and teachers. These communication venues also allow the teachers to recognize the efforts of the parents and somehow motivate them to continue their active involvement in their children's education. Participants also observed that the parents have shown initiative to have one-on-one discussions about the lessons to capacitate themselves (the parents)

in assisting their children at home. This effort resulted in a more effective means of ushering learning and creating better quality outputs.

Alternative Learning/Teaching Methods at Home. This is one of the major interventions made by science teachers to supplement the modules provided. The participants have revealed their propensity to use online sources and videos to facilitate learning. They send the videos or the links to the pupils or parents via online messaging applications. The use of the internet has been seen as game-changer for those pupils who have access to it. Unfortunately, not all pupils enjoy the same access to technology and the internet.

Module/Instruction Modification. Pupils were found to have a hard time comprehending their modules due to the sudden shift in the medium of instruction during their 4th grade from Mother Tongue to English as the main medium of instruction, which is also utilized in the science modules and course books. The participants talked about their initiative to translate the English instructions in modules to the vernacular. They wanted the pupils to still be able to work on their module in case no adults are around to assist them at home.

Pupil Output Quality. This is the first of the two standards for measuring the teachers' sense of accomplishment. The participants utilized the quality of the pupil's output as basis for their (the teachers') level of satisfaction. However, the teachers admitted that they have adjusted their expectations for the pupils given the circumstances of the pandemic. This may have in turn allowed them to feel satisfied with the simple things like pupils' completion of the tasks although the teachers did not specifically describe the quality of the pupils' outputs.

Perception on Teaching Effectiveness. Generally, the teachers show satisfactory self assessment of their effectiveness as a teacher in the midst of the pandemic. As far as teaching effectiveness is concerned, the participants in general graded themselves with a score of 75-80% out of 100% and argued that they could have done better if the circumstances were different. In other words, the participants have a realistic view of their performance. This perception is reflective of their current situations and is influenced by their sense of self-worth.

DISCUSSION

As a science teacher myself, I realized that my battles and circumstances in terms of teaching during this pandemic are one and the same with other science teachers. This realization emboldens me to improve and do better as a teacher. I have also found inspiration in the narratives of the participants as I heard and saw my fellow teachers' level of commitment, passion, and vigor, and their devotion to the teaching profession. Moreover, I felt driven to go out and beyond my comfort zone, to take courage, and to be more steadfast as I overcome whatever lies in the future.

Conclusions

In the light of obtained findings, the researcher concludes that:

First, the participants experienced major changes in their teaching strategies during the pandemic given the circumstances brought by the new modular learning modality. Considering the hindrances in interaction, communication, and learning conditions of the pupils at home, the participants had to make adjustments in the learning instruction. They had to compromise in terms of teaching strategies to accommodate the learners' needs and learning environment at home.

Second, the challenges experienced by the science teacher in terms of teaching conditions include extended working hours, additional work functions, concerns on pupils' output completion and submission, and compromise in academic integrity.

Third, the participants applied various approaches to mitigate the unfavorable conditions in education during the pandemic. They established strong parent-teacher dialogues, provided alternative learning/teaching approaches, and modified the learning materials to cater to the current needs of the pupils.

Fourth, the participants somehow felt a sense of fulfillment and satisfaction with their pupil's output and completion of the modules.

Finally, the science teachers had a realistic perception of their own teaching effectiveness taking into consideration the restrictions and the unique circumstances brought by distance learning during the pandemic.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this qualitative recommended: inquiry, the following are:

1. The Division of Bayawan City may implement the DepEd Order 32 s. 2020 Guideline on the Engagement of Services of Learning Support Aides to Reinforce the Implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan in Time of COVID19 Pandemic.
2. Education Program Supervisors, particularly in the field of science, may encourage the development of laboratory experiments that are feasible and achievable for learners at home.
3. The Department of Education may provide more learning resources for the pupils especially in terms of access to technology and the internet.
4. Schools may strengthen and empower the Parent-Teacher Association to accommodate and resolve issues relevant to modular distance modality.

5. The school heads should be encouraged to conduct an analysis of the immediate needs of the teachers and address the issue on compromise in academic integrity observed by teachers.
6. Teachers may conduct capacity-building activities to parents or include sessions where parents learn from teachers during PTA meetings.
7. Teachers may be encouraged to participate in activities that help improve their self worth, health, and self-confidence.
8. Parents need to be proactive in dealing with the needs of their children at home especially in terms of complying with school requirements and improving the pupils' learning environment/conditions at home.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Since the study is phenomenological in nature, the interview process used guide questions to extract significant statements from the participants. Voluntary participation, informed consent, anonymity and confidentiality, and the dissemination of the risks and benefits of the study were observed in the conduct of the study.

A formal letter was given to the prospective participant indicating a brief introduction of the study and the significance of his or her participation. Target participants were also informed that they could withdraw their participation at any time. The letter also mentioned that the participants would remain anonymous in the study and would be called only through pseudonyms, and that their personal information would be utilized solely in the research.

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